

**APPLICATION OF PEDAGOGICAL EDUCATION METHODS IN
DESIGN ENGINEERING**

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Abstract: The article analyzes the possibilities of improving the design abilities of students, gives recommendations on the formation of design skills, kavlifikaция and on the development of design abilities of students in the circles of applied arts.

Keywords: design education, social activity, art, creativity, aesthetic and artistic activities, design skills

As you know, today the features and capabilities inherent in the art of design are not fully used. The problems arising in this regard are, firstly, the extreme complexity of design activities, and secondly, its relationship with scientific and technical, engineering and design, and economic activities. Thirdly, it is a close connection with the socio-cultural life of society. Therefore, theoretical design problems are multifaceted and require their study at different theoretical stages. While some authors distinguish between the concepts of "Industrial design", "Industrial art", and "industrial aesthetics", other authors call them synonyms.

But the question of the relationship between aesthetic and artistic activities, including semi-luminous illumination, is explained by the fact that design theory lags behind its practice. However, design theory faces a more important task than the ordering of terminology, depending on the extent to which they are solved, the practice of artistic design develops. Without a deep and comprehensive study of these problems, it is impossible to ensure consciously mastered and specifically targeted design activities. This is one of the immediate pedagogical problems.

Although it is recognized that professional activity related to the art of design peaked in England in the middle of the nineteenth century, this reality was noted even earlier in the history of art. Evidence of our opinion is that in 1826 the American Academy of Fine Arts was reorganized and renamed the National Academy of Design. Since 1849, a design magazine ("Journal of Design") began to be published in London. There is a lot of information about the history of design. However, its content is determined by the category of the audience. To familiarize school-age students with the history of design and its theoretical foundations, the information provided should be numerous and not complicated in terms of volume and method of presentation, that is, its practical orientation in design classes should be organized in a priority way. At this time, the reader should have sufficient knowledge that the art of design has gone through complex technological processes on its path of formation and development.

Inspiration is important in creativity, inspiration indicates that all human forces are fully concentrated in the object of creativity, emotionally, spiritually, uplifted, as a result of which work becomes extremely productive. In short, every person should have their own personal opinion. The development of students' design abilities is achieved by developing their knowledge, skills and abilities in this regard. Design knowledge is a systematic perception in the human mind of the concepts and concepts that are tested and tested in practice, necessary for the construction of objects as a product of cognitive activity.

According to the National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan, skill is the ability of a person to carry out a certain activity or action based on previous experience, skills are ways to successfully perform an action in accordance with the goals and conditions of activity related to the ability to apply knowledge in practice.

Skill is the ability to perform actions effectively; skill is an action performed with a certain degree of thoughtfulness; skill is a way to perform an action in a new environment; skill is the mastery of complex systemic mental and practical actions. Based on these definitions, we have determined that a design skill is a way in which a

person masters an activity or action related to design based on their previous experience and successfully performs it according to their circumstances.

While design knowledge is expressed in reasoning in which reality is correctly reflected, design skills are more reflected in mental and physical actions. Design skills are always based on design knowledge and are the foundation of skills. Design qualification is a set of actions with a high degree of assimilation; it is a way of acting, fixed by exercises. The formation and development of design knowledge, skills and abilities of students has its own theoretical and pedagogical features.

Design is considered one of the youngest and fastest growing areas of modern culture. In design activities, scientific and artistic activities, technical creativity manifest themselves synthetically, but design does not become one of them. Although there is something in common between art and design, these are two different types of aesthetic activity. Artistic activity in one form or another is related to the production of things, not just ideas. Accordingly, the designer must have a certain understanding of the engineer, designer, technologist, engineering psychology in a particular production team. The designer's work style is characterized by the embodiment of symbolism and philosophical views. The landscapes and shapes that we see in front of our eyes are actually the perception of information present in the mirror of our mind. Of course, as a result of their perception and perception, we realize a certain meaning and purpose. Otherwise, they will remain in memory as a simple representation.

As you know, the school is a hotbed for the formation of students' creative skills. Students' creative activity is also carried out in applied art lessons, in this process, pedagogical conditions and means of creative thinking of students are important. At the same time, the main organizational form in solving the goals and objectives of developing students' design abilities in applied arts classes is a lesson. The development of students' design abilities is possible not only in art lessons, but also in the process of teaching any subject. In other words, the education and creativity of students is a holistic, holistic pedagogical process.

When teaching visual arts to schoolchildren, along with didactic goals, the teacher must clearly define and solve the goal of developing students' design abilities. For example, mathematics -students' mental creative thinking skills, reading, native language - students' poetic creative thinking skills, natural sciences-students' environmental creative thinking skills, labor - the main means of students' economic and labor creative thinking, music - students' aesthetic creative thinking skills, visual arts - the main means of students' artistic creative thinking, which They are also closely related to the creative thinking skills of other students and complement each other. While music is the main means of aesthetic creative thinking of students, visual arts are the skills of artistic creative thinking of students, they are also closely related to the creative thinking skills of other students and complement each other. With the development of students' design abilities, not only the creative abilities of students, but even educational goals cannot be predetermined in advance. In their development of lesson plans, there are cases when the creative abilities of students are not set before the goals. They will also have a general character if they are marked. The more specific the goal of developing students' creative abilities during the lesson in design lessons, the more convenient it will be to choose ways to achieve it.

Design lessons are of great importance for identifying students' creative abilities. Indeed, in practical creative works on various topics, students manifest moral and aesthetic attitudes, ideas about nature, Homeland, nation, other people, and work. Students' creative abilities can be achieved through good organization, organization of students' creative work. The effectiveness and quality of such classes depend on the comprehensive and thorough training of the head of the circle. On the contrary, unplanned classes dull and weaken students' interest in a particular area. Another of these important requirements is the correspondence of education to the age, individual characteristics and level of knowledge of students.

From the above considerations, it is clear that the demand for design and artistic creativity in life increases every year, as changes, updates and rises of various contents occur in cultural life, in production, in everyday life, etc. In modern conditions, design

is increasingly taking an active part in solving the problems of rational use of natural resources, protection of human health and the environment, which are universal problems. Therefore, the formation and development of students' design abilities in the learning process becomes important in their further activities, maturation as a harmonious personality.

Currently, Technical aesthetics is going through a phase of getting on its feet. Despite the fact that specialists working in this field are extremely active, no complete and rigorous theory has yet developed in understanding design problems. A number of well-known concepts claiming to be a general theory of design, in practice, are associated with its content no more than a reflection of one aspect or another.

To date, several working design definitions have been used. While some authors distinguish between the concepts of "industrial design", "industrial art", and "Industrial aesthetics", others argue that they are synonymous.

Such a variety of forms of posing the question is explained by the fact that the question of the relationship between aesthetic and artistic activities, including semi-luminous illumination, design theory lags behind its practice. However, design theory faces more important tasks than the ordering of terminology, and depending on the extent to which they are solved, the practice of artistic design develops. The problem of harmonization between the production of industrial products and their consumption requires studying the dynamics of public consumption in order to predict their consumption. Without a deep and comprehensive study of these problems, it is impossible to ensure consciously mastered and specifically targeted design activities. To solve this huge problem, first of all, it will be necessary to additionally find a satisfactory answer to the question of the subject and essence of aesthetic public consumption, since aesthetic consumption in general requires an answer to the question of What value is. A satisfactory answer to these questions means building a holistic aesthetic concept. This situation cannot be solved by a single technical aesthetic tool. Building such a concept requires a higher level of technical abstraction with a higher degree. To overcome such difficulties, it will be necessary to work closely with

technical aesthetics, general aesthetics, sociology of art, axiology, semiotics and other sciences. It is commendable that in recent years a close relationship has been established between researchers working in the field of general aesthetics and technical aesthetics. It should also be emphasized that it is not only aesthetic science that needs such assistance provided by other disciplines. But technical aesthetics greatly contributes to the promotion of general aesthetics, once many pressing issues are put on the agenda. Many controversial issues (aesthetic and artistic activity and the ratio of its products, the nature of aesthetic values and their assessment, the problem of the artistic image in fine art, the ratio of forms and functions in the subject, etc.) have appeared before the science of general aesthetics with their new facets.

The visual environment that generates design can provide a more authentic aesthetic characterization of art in a sense. The famous Russian art critic V.V.Stasov wrote at the time: "real, unthinkable folk art exists only where my staircase, my room, my glass, my spoon, my table, my closet, my stove, and my candlestick are beautiful to the last item in this tribe... perhaps there is no need for the small objects necessary for life to be artistic, where art is still growing in the sand, without having had time to put down real roots... The interaction of an aesthetic object (mass production of industrial products) and a subject (mass consumer) is much more convenient for objective research, which allows using a diverse, including statistical method of analysis, all this becomes important in a bold step towards the world of aesthetic Mystery of the century.

The above considerations contribute to the development of the theory of both fields in order to achieve a high level of mutual understanding between specialists in the field of general and technical aesthetics.

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